

67 Bricks Research Plan for OA Books Usage Data Trust

Assignment:

IDS Technical Gap Analysis

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Document information..... 3

 Purpose of document..... 3

 Scope of document..... 3

 References..... 3

Background..... 3

Research outline..... 4

 Business objectives..... 4

 Audience..... 4

 Research questions..... 4

 Scope..... 5

 Process and methodology..... 5

 Information gathering..... 5

 Assumptions..... 6

 Non-technical attributes..... 6

 Technical Criteria..... 6

 Timeline and key dates..... 7

 Mitigation plan..... 8

Deliverables..... 9

Document information

Purpose of document

- To assist 67 Bricks in obtaining and analysing the most relevant information by agreeing the key business objectives for the research
- To agree the approach and scope of the research
- To agree the outputs of the research

It is intended for the following audiences:

- The OAeBUDT stakeholders, to confirm that the approach and outputs will enable them to achieve their business objectives and help lead to the successful delivery of the project.
- The 67 Bricks Engagement Lead, to inform the direction and scope of the research.

Scope of document

This document also describes the agreed business objectives, audience, approach and outputs of the research. It provides further detail on the approach, including proposed timings, areas of focus and methodologies used.

References

This research brief document is based on discussions with Christina Drummond and the OAeBUDT IDS Component Technical Gap Analysis SOW 2023.

Background

The OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAeBUDT) is a scholarly organisation that has a vision of “Community Governed Sharing of Quality, Interoperable, Open Access (OA) Book Usage Data” by pursuing a mission of “championing strategies for the improved publication and management of open-access books by exchanging reliable usage data in a trusted, equitable, and community-governed way.”

To advance the technical development of the trust as an International Data Space (IDS), the OAeBUDT seeks to identify existing platforms and services capable of providing core functional IDS network services to the OAeBUDT. To support the launch of a MVP data space for OA book usage through ideal integration of existing platforms and services, this project will assess operational scholarly publishing service providers (Technical Readiness Levels 7-9) against the IDS core services

described in the Reference Architecture Model 4.0¹ and emerging certification specification documents for interconnected services.

Gap analysis results will be primarily used to identify organisations and/or services in the OA book usage data ecosystem that could perform IDS related functional roles, noting additional development that would be needed to meet certification and security requirements as described in the IDS technical Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM 4.0).

Research outline

Business objectives

The key objective of this work is to identify and assess existing service providers against the IDS requirements for each of the five core IDS data intermediation services to inform the next set of technical work slated for the OAeBUDT, including:

1. The development of the OAeBUDT IDS Technical Research and Development roadmap
2. Systems integration to support an MVP pilot of usage data exchange between two cohorts of <6 OA book usage data providers via IDS core service providers in the IDSA sandbox (2024-2025)
3. Technical roadmap development to explore making the OAeBUDT IDS stack extensible to usage data for other scholarly outputs.

The work will also inform future partnerships and financial modelling.

Audience

The research is being prepared for presentation to and review by the OAeBUDT community governance, including its Executive Director (Christina Drummond), Board, and project advisors. It will be published under a CC-BY licence on Zenodo platform in line with funder requirements.

Research questions

The key goal of the research is to identify and assess existing service providers against the IDS requirements for each of the above five core IDS data intermediation services to inform the next set of technical work slated for the OAeBUDT. Therefore the key questions that will be considered in this work are:

¹ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/ids-ram/>

- What are the broader non-technical attributes of an organisation that may impact their ability to serve as an intermediary service? This is described in more detail under the 'Non-technical attributes' section.
- What are the technical readiness levels of the organisations? Are there any differences in platforms / services offered by the organisation that is more or less technically ready?
- What (if any) additional development (technical and organisational) is needed to meet certification and security requirements as described in the IDS technical RAM?

Scope

The scope for this research is below:

- Ensure transparency to stakeholders of the objectives and purpose of this research work.
- Continual engagement with Christina Drummond and OAeBUDT stakeholders, to develop an understanding of their requirements and goals of the work, and to ensure the work delivered aligns with this. We will attempt to engage with the Project Advisory Board, Technical Advisory Committee and Board of Trustees at least once each throughout the course of the project. See Timeline and Key dates for more information.
- Research in the form of desk research and interviews with pilot organisations and potential intermediary organisations to understand the organisations in more detail, including their current capabilities, challenges, limitations and gaps to meet the IDS provider requirements for a specific IDS role.
- Document our findings and recommendations from the research in the format of a written report, short slide deck (4-6 slides) and an infographic. More details can be found in the Deliverables section.
- IDS Service Roles that will be assessed include: Metadata Broker Service; IDS Clearing House; App Store Provider; Vocabulary Providers; Identity Provider
- It is out of scope to identify or evaluate producers, providers or consumers of usage data. Should an identified candidate for one of the IDS Service Roles also create usage data or host a usage metrics related platform or service for others, that will be noted.

Process and methodology

Information gathering

The primary methods used during the course of the engagement are desk research and interviews. The initial desk research will provide the foundational information on organisations already identified in the statement of work, and identify and consider those not already listed. This initial work will then inform which organisations should be contacted for subsequent interviews, which will aim to

gather more detailed information that could not be obtained from the desk research alone (i.e. from internal collective 67 Bricks expertise or reviewing publicly available information). Information gathered and potential organisations to be considered will be discussed and reviewed with OAeBUDT throughout the engagement. We have provided below an outline of what will be examined throughout the course of the work and included in the final report.

Assumptions

This research plan has been developed with the assumption that there will be a level of engagement with the IDSA (e.g. via call or email) to provide additional information on the assessment criteria for certification that is not already publicly available. Any limitations identified during discussions with the IDSA will be incorporated into the research plan and an updated version circulated for review.

Non-technical attributes

A number of organisational criteria will be assessed to provide a broader context for which the technical criteria can be considered. This will include:

- **Country of legal incorporation** - Which country the organisation is legally incorporated in.
- **Countries serviced** - List of countries / world regions the organisation currently operates within.
- **Country of data processing** - Which countries the organisation actually stores / processes data within, this can influence issues around data sharing (e.g. between EU and US based organisations), which in turn impacts the roles they are best suited to.
- **Currently supported content types** - e.g. closed books, open data, journal articles etc
- **Staffing** - Is the organisation primarily run by volunteers, staffed part or full time?
- **Governance model:** whether the organisation is commercial, not for profit or public. Definitions will be provided for clarity.
- **Age** - Is the organisation less than 1 year old, less than 2 years old, less than 10 years old or greater than 10 (SCOSS definition)? Older organisations are more likely to continue existing; though they may have more technical debt and be less able to innovate than younger organisations.

Technical Criteria

Through the collaboration with the IDS during this engagement, both from existing published documentation and meetings with them, we will have an understanding of and access to the detailed criteria to assess how close organisations are to certification for each of the five core intermediation

services. Our assessment will therefore be based on this, in addition to the publicly available documentation^{2,3,4}.

We will use this information to develop questionnaires (using a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessments) to work through with potential partners. The questions will be based on factors required for certification and to identify a suitable technical readiness level and draw attention to any gaps.

Timeline and key dates

Month	Research Activity	Deliverable timeline	Team Availability Notes
November	Research plan development Desk research 28 Nov - Catch-up	Nov 15 - Draft delivered Nov 20 - research begins	Nov 13-17 - Richard Brown on leave Nov 20-24 - Alexandra Howat on leave Nov 22 - 27 - Christina Drummond on leave
December	Desk research Present research plan Dec 13 Obtain OAeBUDT BoT feedback on high level research plan and list of organisations identified and roles 12 Dec - Project Team Catch-up with Christina Drummond	Dec 1 - Final research plan approved Dec 8 - Send out invites to organisations identified as potential service providers and pilot organisations, for interviews in January Dec 20 - IDSA meeting	Dec 11-12 Christina Drummond at CNI Conference - limited availability Dec 18-Jan 1 Christina Drummond on leave Dec 25-Jan 1 67 Bricks on leave
January	Interview pilot organisations and potential intermediary services (Date TBD early Jan) - Obtain Technical Advisory	Feb 5 - Draft report / slide / infosheet provided	Jan 15, 17 Christina Drummond on leave

² <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/ids-ram-4/>

³ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/white-papers/>

⁴ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/position-papers/>

	<p>Committee feedback on identified organisations and roles</p> <p>(Date TBD) - Obtain Project Advisory Board feedback on identified organisations and roles</p>		
February	Project closeout	Feb 12 - Final deliverables provided	<p>Feb 11-14 Christina Drummond at NISO+ Conference - limited availability</p> <p>Feb 19-23 Christina Drummond at R2R Conference - limited availability</p>

Mitigation plan

We recognise that the timeline for scheduling interviews with pilot organisations and potential service providers is tight in this engagement, and therefore there is a risk of being unable to speak to them directly. We have therefore set out the following mitigation plan:

1. Send out invitations for interviews to organisations identified as pilot organisations or potential service providers by 15 December, with the offer of interviews to be scheduled in January.
2. In the cases where we can't secure interviews (organisations do not respond or do not have time before Feb 12) we will send out questionnaires for some structured feedback, and we will caveat in the final report the slight limitation that this form of feedback has without the additional context provided from interviews

Deliverables

For each of the following deliverables, draft versions will be shared with OA Book Usage Data Trust representatives and community stakeholders for a planned feedback cycle. Final versions will include adjustments made in response to feedback received. All deliverables will be provided without restriction for open publishing under a CC-BY-4.0 licence.

Deliverable	Description
Research Plan	Document describing the agreed business objectives, audience, approach and outputs of the research. It provides further detail on the approach, including proposed timings, areas of focus and methodologies used.
Questionnaire(s)	A document containing a combination of qualitative and quantitative assessments to work through with potential partner organisations. The questions will be based on factors required for certification and to identify a suitable technical readiness level and draw attention to any gaps. Development of this is also based on discussions with IDSA.
Findings Report	Document that will include an executive summary and analysis details for each of the IDS component services and potential providers reviewed. It will conclude by making recommendations of potential service providers capable of providing a certifiable IDS component service and/or gaps found in individual organisations that require further research and development to fulfil.
Findings Slide Deck	Slide deck of approximately 4-6 slides summarising the report methodology, results, and recommendations. These slides will be presented to the OA Book Usage Data Trust's Board of Trustees and speaking notes will be included so that project staff can reuse the slides to present the methodology, findings and results independently as needed.
Findings Summary Infographic	A one-page infographic that summarises the completed work and findings for scholarly publication stakeholder audiences.